

Effects of granular herbicides and hand weeding on weed wt and rice yield. West Bengal, India.

Treatment ^a	Dry wt of weeds at 60 DT (g/m ²)	Yield of rice grain (t/ha)
Fluchloralin 1.5 kg 1 DBT	19.05	2.9
Fluchloralin 2.0 kg 1 DBT	16.81	3.0
Fluchloralin 1.5 kg 1 DT	13.46	2.8
Fluchloralin 2.0 kg 1 DT	11.34	2.7
Fluchloralin 1.5 kg 7 DT	10.04	3.2
Fluchloralin 2.0 kg 7 DT	6.48	3.7
Butachlor 1.5 kg 6 DT	5.74	3.5
Butachlor 2.0 kg 6 DT	3.92	3.6
Nitrofen 1.5 kg 6 DT	3.93	3.4
Nitrofen 2.0 kg 6 DT	2.23	3.8
Hand weeding, 25 & 50 DT	3.82	3.5
Unweeded control	52.95	2.3
S.Em ±	2.71	.06
C.D. at 5% level	8.40	1.90

^aDBT = days before transplanting, DT = days after transplanting. All herbicide doses are in active ingredient per hectare.

controlling all categories of weeds. Fluchloralin 2.0 kg a.i./ha at 7 DT showed very effective reduction of broadleaved and grass weeds. The dry weight of weeds at 60 DT was very much reduced after the application of nitrofen at 6 DT, butachlor at 6 DT, and fluchloralin at 7 DT compared to the other treatments. Nitrofen granules at 2 kg ai/ha applied 6 DT gave the highest yield of rice grain, closely followed by fluchloralin 2.0 kg a.i./ha at 7 DT, butachlor (G) 2.0 kg a.i./ha at 6 DT, and 2 hand weedings. As high as 37.69% loss in grain yield was observed with no weeding compared with the best treatment (nitrofen 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT). ■

Weed control in deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, deepwater rice is also known as broadcast aman (b. aman) rice because the seeds are sown by broadcasting in March-April with the first monsoon showers. As in any direct-seeded rice, weeds are a serious problem in the deepwater rice crop. Farmers in

Bangladesh with about 2 million ha (about 20% of the total rice area) of deepwater rice use raking, laddering, and hand weeding to control weeds in the b. aman rice fields. Sometimes the farmers allow the weeds to grow to a certain height and then use them as fodder, which commands a good market price in the deepwater rice belt.

In 1980, farmers' weed control practices at the BRRI deepwater rice-based cropping systems research site at Daudkandi were monitored. The results showed that, on the average, 1, 2, and 3 hand weedings were done by 22.5, 67.5, and 10% of the farmers (see table). The average time for hand weedings was 33 days after seeding (DS) for the first

hand weeding, 51 DS for the second, and 75 DS for the third.

Triple hand weedings were used on two popular varieties Kartiksail and Sada Pankaish, the third weeding applied between 73 and 89 DS. Double hand weeding as practised in Ejuli Khama and Dulai Aman was completed between 44 and 54 DS. A small number of farmers grew varieties Bhatial Bajal and An Raj and applied only one hand weeding either at a very delayed (58 DS) or a very early (11 DS) date, but within 29 April and 7 May, the time of first flush of weeds after the initial monsoon rains (see table). More detailed weed studies at the site are planned. ■

Frequency and timing of farmers' hand weeding in the 1980 deepwater rice crop at the BRRI cropping systems research site, Daudkandi, Comilla district, Bangladesh.^a

Deepwater rice variety	Samples (no.)	Av seeding date	Farmers (%) applying			Time of HW (DS)			Maturity (DS)
			1 HW	2 HW	3 HW	1st HW	2d HW	3d HW	
Kartiksail	18	9 Apr	11	72	17	27	49	13	215
Sada Pankaish	8	11 Apr	24	63	13	30	55	89	221
Ejuli Khama	8	15 Apr	12	88	—	21	44	—	206
Dulai Aman	3	2 Apr	33	67	—	35	54	—	230
Bhatial Bajal	2	30 Mar	100	—	—	58	—	—	230
Ari Raj	1	26 Apr	100	—	—	11	—	—	201
Av		10 Apr	22.5	67.5	10	33	51	75	216

^aHW = hand weeding, DS = days after seeding.

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